

Considerations on Coupled Oscillator Entanglement Entropy

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In (1) an interesting calculation of the entanglement entropy of a coupled two oscillator system ground state $|0\rangle\langle 0|$ is presented using the von Neumann reduced density matrix. In this note we wish to focus on two points. First it is stated that the reduced density matrix (in a spatial basis) has an angular frequency w of $\sqrt{w^+ w^-}$ (where w^+ and w^- are defined later). We find this frequency is linked to wavefunctions before a trace over a second spatial variable is performed and that the final angular frequency is different.

Secondly, it is stated that the reduced density matrix “happens” (1) to represent that of a single oscillator. We try to show that this follows from the mathematical form of the spatial density matrix written in terms of a product of two single oscillator spatial density matrices. The orthonormality of the basis functions $H_n(x_b)$ and $H_j(x_b)$ of the second spatial variable force the two basis functions $H_n(x_a)H_j(x_a)$ to become $H_n(x_a)H_n(x_a)$ and leads to a spatial density matrix of a single oscillator, so such a result is anticipated.

We write a product of ground state oscillator wavefunctions in variables x_a+x_b and x_a-x_b in terms of the density of a single oscillator i.e. $\sum_n \exp(-E_n/T) H_n(x_a)H_n(x_b)$. We do a similar thing for the two similar functions in x_a' and x_b' . Setting $x_b=x_b'$ and integrating leads to a single oscillator density form. The problem is that the w and T for this result do not match the w and T of the final result obtained by integrating the product of four ground states with $x_b=x_b'$. Thus there may be an issue with integrating before summing. In other words, summing $\sum_n \exp(-E_n/T) H_n(x_a)H_n(x_b)$ and separately summing $\sum_j \exp(-E_j/T) H_j(x_a')H_j(x_b)$ and then multiplying and integrating over dx_b yields a single oscillator density form, but for a particular w_1, T_1 . Integrating $\int dx_b H_j(x_b)H_n(x_b) = \delta_{(n,j)}$ before summing leads again to a single oscillator spatial density, but with a different w_2 and T_2 . Only one set w, T for a single oscillator should map into the integrated result.

Coupled Oscillator

The standard Hamiltonian for two coupled oscillators is given in (1) by:

$$p_1^2/2 + p_2^2/2 + .5 w_1 w_1 (x_a x_a + x_b x_b) + .5 w_2 w_2 (x_a x_a - x_b x_b) \quad ((1))$$

Changing variables to $y_1=(x_a+x_b)$ and $y_2=(x_a-x_b)$ leads to a decoupled Hamiltonian i.e.

$$-1/2m d/dy_1 d/dy_1 -1/2m d/dy_2 d/dy_2 + .5w^+w^+ (x_a+x_b)(x_a+x_b) +.5w^-w^- (x_a-x_b)(x_a-x_b) \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Where } w^+w^+ = w_1w_1 \quad \text{and } w^-w^- = w_1w_1 + 2 w_2w_2 \quad ((3))$$

Choosing the ground state $|0\rangle\langle 0|$ one has a product of two ground state single oscillator wavefunctions, one in y_1 and the other in y_2 . This wavefunction is of the form of a Gaussian. Thus:

$\langle x'a \ x'b \mid \text{dab} \mid x_a \ x_b \rangle$ is proportional to
 $\exp\{ -.5w+(x_a+x_b)(x_a+x_b) - .5w-(x_a-x_b)(x_a-x_b) - .5w+(x'a+x'b)(x'a+x'b) - .5w-(x'a-x'b)(x'a-x'b) \}$

((4)) from (1)

These are simply four ground state single particle Gaussian wavefunctions in the variables (x_a+x_b) , (x_a-x_b) , $(x'a+x'b)$ and $(x'a-x'b)$.

At this point we quote the mathematical form of single particle oscillator von Neumann density in a spatial basis i.e.

$$\text{Sum over } n \quad \langle x'a \mid n \rangle \exp(-En/T) \langle n \mid x_a \rangle = \text{Sum over } n \quad H_n(x'a)H_n(x_a) \exp(-w(n+.5)/T) \quad ((5))$$

Here $H_n(x_a)$ is $\exp(-.5b \ xx)$ Hermite polynomial $n(x_a)$ where b is a constant.

Summing over n in ((5)) yields (as given in (2)) ($m=1$ and $\hbar=1$)

Single oscillator $\langle x'a \ \text{da} \ x_a \rangle$

$$\text{proportional to } \exp\{ .25w \{ A (x_a+x'a)(x_a+x'a) + 1/A (x_a-x'a')(x_a-x'a) \} \} \quad ((6))$$

Where $A=\tanh(w/2T)$.

We argue that the ground state single oscillator wavefunction product in ((4)) may be written in terms of ((6)). Given that there are four wavefunctions in the product, we will use this approach twice.

$$\exp\{ -.5w+(x_a+x_b)(x_a+x_b) - .5w-(x_a-x_b)(x_a-x_b) \} = \text{Sum over } n \quad H_n(x'a)H_n(x_a) \exp(-w(n+.5)/T) \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{Thus: } .25wA = .5w+ \quad \text{and} \quad .25w/A = .5w- \quad \text{or} \quad .25 \ ww = w+w- \quad \text{or} \quad w = 2 \ \text{sqrt}(w+ \ w-) \quad ((8))$$

In (1) it is stated that after taking the Trace over x_b , one has a single oscillator with frequency $\text{sqrt}(w+ \ w-)$. We try to link this value to ((8)) which is a mathematical result for the x_a , x_b combined wavefunctions.

As a result, we rewrite ((4)) as being proportional to:

$$\{ \text{Sum over } n \quad H_n(x_a)H_n(x_b) \exp(-2w(n+.5)/T) \} \{ \text{Sum over } j \quad H_j(x'a)H_j(x'b) \} \quad ((9))$$

Taking the Trace over x_b i.e. setting $x_b=x_b'$ and integrating over dx_b using:

$$\text{Integral } dx_b \quad H_n(x_b)H_j(x_b) = \delta(n,b) \quad ((10))$$

Then:

$$\text{Reduced density} = \sum_n H_n(x_a)H_n(x'_a) \exp(-2w(n+.5)/T) \quad ((11))$$

At this point T is unknown, but a main point we wish to make is that the reduced density ((11)) is of the form of the spatial von Neumann density of a single oscillator. One may note the extra factor of 2 in $\exp()$. One may write $T=T/2$. Secondly, one must note that the Hermite wavefunctions are in a variable $x \sqrt{\sqrt{2} \sqrt{w+ w-}}$. In particular, one has $w=2\sqrt{w+ w-}$ and a corresponding unique $T=T/2$. The problem is that if one sets $x_b=x'_b$ in ((4)) and integrates, one obtains the von Neumann spatial density for a single oscillator, but with a different w and T . Even the ratio w/T differs. This is a problem because the reduced entropy (as will be seen later) depends only on w/T , so the two approaches yield different entanglement entropies. One possible issue may be that in writing two of the functions in terms of an infinite sum of product $H_n(x_a)H_n(x_b)$'s and the other two in terms of $H_j(x'_a)H_j(x_b)$ and integrating over dx_b , one integrates before one sums, leading to one result. Summing first and then integrating seems to lead to a different result although in both cases the form is that of a single oscillator.

Given that T is unknown, one would have to solve ((11)) in terms of this unknown. One may, however, set $x_b=x'_b$ in ((4)) and integrate over dx_b to obtain a result strictly in terms of $w+$, $w-$, x_a and x'_a . This result is given in (1) as:

Reduced density is proportional to:

$$\text{Exp}\{ [2(w+ - w-)(w+ - w-)x'_a x_a - (8w+w- + (w+ - w-)(w+ - w-)(x_a x_a + x'_a x'_a))] / (8(w++ w-)) \} \quad ((12))$$

This is of the form of a single oscillator reduced density matrix. From ((12)) one may factor out:

$(w+ - w-)(w+ - w-)$ so that:

$$\cosh(w/T) = [(8w+w- + (w+ - w-)(w+ - w-)) / (w+ - w-)(w+ - w-)] = M \quad ((13))$$

At this point T and w are not known, but this is not necessary for the calculation of the entanglement entropy, one the ratio w/T is needed, which may be found from ((13)). It may be seen from ((13)) that $\cosh(w/T) > 1$ and positive which is required of the function.

From ((13)) one has $\cosh(z)$ and $\sinh z = \sqrt{-1+MM}$ where $M(w+,w-)$. Then from ((12))

$$(w+ - w-)(w+ - w-) = .5 w_1 \sinh(z) \quad ((14))$$

where we use w_1 because it does not equal $2\sqrt{w+w-}$. ((14)) then yields:

$$W_{full} = 2(w_+ - w_-)(w_+ + w_-) / \sqrt{-1 + MM(w_+, w_-)} \quad ((15))$$

with M given by ((13)). Using numbers as an example e.g. $w_+=1$ and $w_-=2$ one finds that $\sinh(w/T) = 4$ so $w_{full} = .5$. $2\sqrt{w_+w_-} = 2\sqrt{2}$ which is completely different.

Thus w_{full} and $2\sqrt{w_+w_-}$ seem to differ. It may be noted that as given in (1), the von Neumann entropy of a single oscillator only depends on w/T . In this problem one does not know T the temperature associated with entanglement. ((12)), the reduced matrix has neither a T nor a w. As shown by ((13)) and ((15)) one may find values of w_1 and z and hence T as functions of w_+, w_- , but it is only the ratio $z=w_1/T_1$ that is needed.

((4)) suggests that the reduced matrix should be that of a single oscillator, but the exact calculation ((12)) should be used to yield w_{full} and T. In (1) equation ((13)) is used to yield a result for w/T . In (1) it is stated that $w=\sqrt{w_+w_-}$, but this seems inconsistent with ((13)) and the form of single oscillator reduced density.

In (1) the entanglement entropy is given by:

$$-\sum \ln(b_n) \quad \text{where } b_n \text{ are the eigenvalues } \exp(-w/T(n+.5)) / C(T). \quad ((16))$$

$$\text{Specifically: } S = (w/T) / \{\exp(w/T) - 1\} + \ln(1 - \exp(-w/T)) \quad ((17))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion we examine the calculation of entangled entropy for two coupled quantum oscillators provided in (1). In (1) it is stated that the reduced spatial density matrix “happens” to be that of an oscillator. We try to show why this should be anticipated although this involves integrating before summing an infinite series which seems to lead to problems in the values of w and T.

Secondly, it is stated that $w=\sqrt{w_+w_-}$ for the single oscillator, but setting $x_b=x'_b$ (i.e. taking a trace) and integrating over dx_b seems to lead to a form with a different angular frequency. The value $\sqrt{w_+w_-}$ seems to be linked to a mathematical angular frequency if one considers the product of two ground state Gaussian single oscillator functions (which appears in the calculation before the trace and integral over db are performed).

In other words, if one integrates the product of four ground state wavefunctions in (x_a-x_b) , (x'_a-x_b) , (x_a+x_b) and $(x'_a + x_b)$ variables one finds a single oscillator density result, but for a different w and T. The value $\sqrt{w_+w_-}$ seems to be linked to writing the product of two ground state wavefunctions in terms of $\sum_n \exp(-E_n/T) H_n(x_a)H_n(x_b)$ and the product of the other two as $\sum_j \exp(-E_j/T) H_j(x'_a)H_j(x_b)$ and then integrating before summing i.e. $\int dx_b H_n(x_b)H_j(x_b) = \delta(n,j)$. This leads to a single oscillator result with a different w and T. Thus changing the order of summation and integration leads to two different results, but one may only use a unique w,T. Thus the summation first approach of (1) seems to apply.

References

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